

STROBE Checklist for "An Assessment of Professional Burnout within Hospital Pharmacists: A Case Study of Abu Dhabi"

The following is a completed **STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) Checklist** based on the relevant manuscript. Each checklist item is addressed with corresponding information extracted from the manuscript to ensure comprehensive and transparent reporting of the study.

Title and Abstract

1. Title and Abstract

- **1a. Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - **Title:** The title includes "A Case Study," which is a general term indicating a cross-sectional design.
 - **Abstract:** The abstract mentions that the study is cross-sectional.
 - **1b. Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The abstract provides a clear summary of the study's introduction, background, aim, methods, results, and conclusion. It outlines the objective to assess burnout rates, the use of the Maslach Burnout Inventory, the response rate, key findings, and the need for further investigation.
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Introduction

2. Background/Rationale

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The introduction comprehensively covers the definition of burnout, its dimensions, historical context, and its relevance in healthcare settings. It

highlights the gap in research regarding burnout among hospital pharmacists in the United Arab Emirates, thereby justifying the need for the study.

3. Objectives

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The study clearly states its objective: "To assess the rate of burnout among hospital pharmacists working in Sheikh Khalifa Medical City." It further specifies the aim to use a validated tool (MBI-HSS MP) to measure burnout levels.
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Methods

4. Study Design

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript specifies that the study is a "single-center, cross-sectional study" conducted at Sheikh Khalifa Medical City (SKMC) in Abu Dhabi, UAE.

5. Setting

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The setting is thoroughly described as SKMC, a Joint Commission International-accredited hospital with a 560-bed capacity, providing inpatient and outpatient services. The data collection period is specified as a two-week period starting on June 20, 2022.

6. Participants

- **6a. Eligibility Criteria, Sources, and Methods of Selection**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - **Eligibility Criteria:** Inclusion criteria include licensed pharmacists employed at SKMC in any pharmacy practice setting. Exclusion criteria include pharmacy technicians, residents, clerks, interns, or any non-pharmacist staff.
 - **Sources and Methods of Selection:** Recruitment involved sending an email to pharmacy managers, who then informed their teams. The primary researcher visited each pharmacy area, provided a verbal

explanation, and distributed surveys in sealed envelopes.
Participation was voluntary, and surveys were returned anonymously.

7. Variables

- **Fulfilled:**
 - **Outcomes:** Burnout measured using the Maslach Burnout Inventory – Human Services Survey for Medical Professionals (MBI-HSS MP), encompassing emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment subscales.
 - **Exposures/Predictors:** Demographic variables including age, gender, marital status, highest pharmacy qualification, years of professional practice at SKMC, and current pharmacy practice setting.
 - **Potential Confounders:** The study considers demographic factors but does not explicitly define potential confounders beyond these variables.

8. Data Sources/Measurement

- **Fulfilled:**
 - **Sources of Data:** The Maslach Burnout Inventory – Human Services Survey for Medical Personnel (MBI-HSS MP) was used alongside supplementary demographic questions.
 - **Methods of Assessment:** The MBI-HSS MP consists of 22 items measured on a 7-point Likert scale. Demographic information was collected through supplementary questions.
 - **Comparability:** Surveys were administered in hard copy to ensure consistency and prevent technical issues, maintaining comparability across all participants.

9. Bias

- **Fulfilled:**
 - **Addressing Bias:** The study addresses potential biases by ensuring anonymity through sealed envelopes, voluntary participation, and informed consent.

10. Study Size

- **Fulfilled:**

- **Explanation of Study Size:** The manuscript reports a response rate of 75.5% (68 out of 90 pharmacists) and it provides a rationale for the sample size in “Sample Size Determination” section.

11. Quantitative Variables

- **Fulfilled:**
 - **Handling Quantitative Variables:** Burnout scores are categorized based on established thresholds (low, moderate, high) as per Maslach et al. (2018). The rationale for categorization is based on previous research indicating the reliability of these thresholds.
 - **Groupings:** The manuscript clearly defines the score ranges for each burnout category in Table 1, aligning with standardized classifications.

12. Statistical Methods

- **12a. Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript details the use of SPSS version 28 for data analysis, employing descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation) and inferential statistics such as univariate analysis, Spearman’s rho correlation, and multiple regression to explore associations between demographic factors and burnout levels.
- **12b. Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The study conducts subgroup analyses based on demographic factors but does not extensively examine subgroups.
- **12c. Explain how missing data were addressed**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript notes instances of missing demographic data (e.g., educational level) and elaborates on specific methods used to handle missing data (e.g. “such missing responses were excluded from statistical tests involving educational level to prevent any bias”).

- **12d. Describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The study accounts for sampling across different pharmacy settings, detailed adjustments for sampling design are provided in “Sample size determination”.
 - **12e. Describe any sensitivity analyses**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - It is clarified in the Methods section under Data Analysis that practice settings were included as independent variables in the multiple regression analysis.
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Results

13. Participants

- **13a. Report numbers at each stage**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript reports that 90 pharmacists were approached, with 68 participating (response rate of 75.5%). It also details the distribution of participants across various pharmacy sites.
- **13b. Give reasons for non-participation**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript does mentions reasons for non-participation among the 22 pharmacists who did not respond (“Non-participation among some pharmacists was primarily attributed to reported time constraints and personal reluctance to engage in research activities”).
- **13c. Consider use of a flow diagram**
 - **Not Fulfilled:**
 - A flow diagram was not included as the uniform recruitment process and high response rate are clearly described in the text, making a visual representation unnecessary for understanding the study's participant flow.

14. Descriptive Data

- **14a. Characteristics of study participants**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - Demographic characteristics such as age distribution, gender, marital status, educational level, years of practice, and practice settings are comprehensively reported in Table 2.
- **14b. Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript mentions missing data for educational level and specific responses.

15. Outcome Data

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript presents detailed outcome data, including the number of pharmacists categorized under each burnout level across the MBI subscales, as shown in Table 3. It also discusses the classification of pharmacists into high, moderate, and low burnout categories.

16. Main Results

- **16a. Give unadjusted and confounder-adjusted estimates**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript provides unadjusted estimates through descriptive statistics and presents inferential statistics results, including correlation coefficients and regression analysis, indicating the lack of significant associations between demographic factors and burnout levels.
- **16b. Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized**
 - **Fulfilled:**
 - The classification criteria for burnout levels based on MBI scores are clearly outlined in Table 1.
- **16c. Consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk**

- **Not Applicable:**
 - The study design focuses on assessing prevalence rather than risk factors, making relative and absolute risk estimates less relevant.

17. Other Analyses

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript includes univariate and multivariate regression analyses to explore associations between demographic factors and burnout levels. While it mentions Spearman's rho correlation and multiple regression, detailed subgroup or interaction analyses are not extensively discussed.
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Discussion

18. Key Results

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The discussion section effectively summarizes the key findings, such as the prevalence of high burnout (25%), the lack of significant associations with demographic factors, and the higher representation of females in the high burnout category. It relates these findings to existing literature and highlights the study's contributions.

19. Limitations

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript discusses several limitations, including:
 - Preference for electronic surveys over paper-based surveys.
 - Language difficulties faced by some participants, leading to struggles in responding.
 - Applicability issues of certain survey questions to specific pharmacy settings.
 - The inability to identify causes of burnout due to the study design.

20. Interpretation

- **Fulfilled:**

- The authors cautiously interpret the results, acknowledging the lack of significant associations while discussing findings in the context of existing literature. They suggest organizational strategies to mitigate burnout and highlight areas for future research, such as assessing burnout among other pharmacy roles and identifying specific causes.

21. Generalisability

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript discusses the study being conducted in a single center (SKMC) and suggests the need for broader research across different pharmacy roles and settings in Abu Dhabi and the UAE to enhance generalizability. It acknowledges that findings may not be directly applicable to other settings without further studies.
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Other Information

22. Funding

- **Fulfilled:**
 - The manuscript clearly states that the study was not funded and that the authors declare no potential conflicts of interest.

Additional Information:

- **Consent to Participate:**
 - Detailed in the manuscript, indicating that all participants provided written informed consent. The consent process was approved by the University of Bradford Ethical Committee, and confidentiality was assured.
- **Data Availability:**
 - The manuscript provides links to the Zenodo repository for underlying and extended data, ensuring transparency and reproducibility. Data are available under the Creative Commons Zero "No rights reserved" data waiver (CC0 1.0).
- **Reporting Guidelines:**
 - The study adheres to the STROBE guidelines, as stated in the manuscript, ensuring comprehensive reporting of observational study elements.

